

Synthesis of vinyl-terminated Au nanoprisms and nanooctahedra mediated by 3-butenic acid: direct Au@pNIPAM fabrication with improved SERS capabilities†

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Here we describe the first seedless synthesis of vinyl-terminated Au nanotriangular prisms (AuNTPs) and nanooctahedra (AuNOC) in aqueous media. This synthesis is performed by chemical reduction of chloroauric acid (HAuCl₄) with 3-butenic acid (3BA) in the presence of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride (BDAC). The principal novelties of the presented method are the use of a mixture of 3BA and BDAC, the synthesis of gold prisms and octahedra with controllable size, and the presence of terminal double bonds on the metal surface. Initially this method produces a mixture of triangular gold nanoprisms and octahedra; however, both morphologies are successfully separated by surfactant micelle induced depletion interaction, reaching percentages up to ~90%. Moreover, the alkene moieties present on the gold surface are exploited for the fabrication of hybrid core@shell particles. Gold octahedra and triangular prisms are easily encapsulated by free radical polymerization of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM). Finally, in order to obtain a gold core with the most number of tips, AuNTP@pNIPAM microgels were subjected to gold core overgrowth, thus resulting in star-shaped nanoparticles (AuSTs@pNIPAM). We use 4-aminobenzenethiol as the model analyte for SERS investigations. As expected, gold cores with tips and high curvature sites produced the highest plasmonic responses.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the interest in the fabrication of noble metal nanoparticles with a great variety of sizes and morphologies is motivated by the advances in the understanding of their synthesis and properties,^{1,2} as well as the possibility of being applied in a vast number of fields such as drug delivery,^{3,4} DNA analysis,^{5,6} cancer diagnosis⁸ and treatment,^{9,10} immunoassay,⁷ and SERS and catalytic investigations.^{11,12}

The properties of noble metal nanoparticles arise from the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR),^{13,14} which remarkably depends, among other factors, on particle size and shape.^{13,15} Since the first synthesis concerning gold nano-

particles only produced spherical shapes,¹⁶ significant efforts have been made to develop synthetic routes for the fabrication of non-spherical morphologies. This interest in the synthesis of anisotropic metal nanoparticles is due to the fact that morphologies containing well-defined angles or tips possess more localized plasmons, thus leading to further promising and attractive applications in the aforementioned fields.^{17,18}

During the last few decades, several protocols regarding the synthesis of particles with different morphologies such as triangles, rods, wires, octahedra, decahedra, cages or stars have been reported in water or organic media.^{19–25} Colloidal suspensions of Au nanoparticles are typically prepared by the reaction of a gold salt with a reducing agent, in the presence of stabilizing “capping” molecules, which play an important role in controlling the nanoparticle morphology.^{22,26–31} Concerning the fabrication of Au octahedra and triangular prisms, which are the morphologies fabricated in this work, several protocols have been reported. For instance, Xia *et al.* reported the synthesis of gold octahedra by reducing HAuCl₄ with *N*-vinylpyrrolidone in an aqueous solution in the presence of cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC).²¹ Mirkin *et al.* fabricated gold octahedra, in high yield, *via* the controlled over-

growth of preformed seeds by Ag⁺-assisted, seed-mediated synthesis.²⁷ Liz-Marzán *et al.* obtained Au nanotriangles by using CTAC-capped gold nanoparticles as seeds, in the presence of small amounts of iodide ions, and using ascorbic acid as a reducing agent.³² More recently, a seedless approach to synthesize monodisperse Au nanotriangles in high yield (>90%) has been reported by Zhang *et al.*³³ Unfortunately, all these methods give rise to particles solely stabilized by surfactants, that is, with no other functional groups on the metal surface, that could be readily available for use in further chemical reactions.

Nowadays, a lot of research effort is devoted to the synthesis of nanocomposite materials with a core-shell architecture. Such hybrid systems are typically composed of a metal core encapsulated within a polymer shell.³⁴ These nanocomposite materials have been demonstrated to display a better performance for sensing and catalytic purposes compared with pure metal nanoparticles.³⁴⁻³⁷ They could also incorporate multiple functionalities and this improves their colloidal stability.³⁸⁻⁴¹ However, to obtain such a core-shell morphology a surface modification step of the nanoparticles surface is generally required. Recently, butenoic acid has been used as a reducing agent for the synthesis of spherical and octahedral Au nanoparticles.^{42,43} Additionally, this molecule incorporates terminal double bonds on the particle surface, which has been exploited for the fabrication of core@shellAu@pNIPAM hybrid nanocomposites systems.^{38,42}

Herein, we report a water-based seedless method for the synthesis of vinyl-terminated triangular Au nanoprisms and nanooctahedra with controllable size, with 3-butenoic acid acting as reducing as well as shape inducing agents. Initially, two main morphologies were obtained: triangular prisms (AuNTPs) and octahedra (AuNOCs). We analyze the influence of the temperature and gold salt concentration in the reaction mixture on the shape and size of the particles. Both morphologies were successfully separated by surfactant micelle induced depletion interaction.^{44,45} Additionally, the presence of terminal double bonds on the Au nanoparticle surface (coming from 3BA) was exploited for the fabrication of core@shell hybrid systems by free radical polymerization of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM), including octahedra, prisms and star-like (AuSTs@pNIPAM) gold cores. Finally, the SERS enhancement capabilities of the different core-shell hybrids were studied using 4-aminobenzenethiol (4ABT) as the model analyte.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

3-Butenoic acid (3BA, 97%), cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC, ≥98%), benzyldimethylhexadecylammonium chloride (BDAC, ≥97%), *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM, 97%) and 4-aminobenzenethiol (4ABT, 97%) were supplied by Aldrich. HAuCl₄·3H₂O (≥99.9% trace metal basis) was supplied by Sigma. *N,N'*-Methylenebisacrylamide (BIS, ≥99.5%) was

supplied by Fluka. 2,2'-Azobis(2-methylpropionamidine) dihydrochloride (AAPH, 97%) was supplied by Acros Organics. All reactants were used without further purification. Water was purified using a Milli-Q system (Millipore).

2.2 Characterization methods

UV-vis measurements of aqueous colloidal solutions were recorded with a HP Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were acquired on a JEOL JEM 1400 operating at an acceleration voltage of 80 kV. Samples were prepared by drying a 10 μL drop of colloidal suspension on a carbon-coated copper grid. HR-TEM images were acquired with a JEOL JEM2010F field-emission gun transmission electron microscope working at 200 kV. For this specific analysis, samples were prepared letting dry a drop of sample on TEM copper grids coated with holey carbon thin films. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) images were obtained in a Helios Nanolab 650 Dual Beam from FEI, working at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV, a current intensity of 0.2 nA and a tilting angle of 52°. Samples were prepared by dropping 20 μL of an aqueous colloidal solution onto a 1 × 1 cm single side polished boron-doped silicon (111) wafer (WRS Materials). SERS spectra were recorded using a confocal Raman microscope (CRM) alpha300R (WITec GmbH, Ulm, Germany). SERS signals were recorded by exciting the colloidal solutions with a laser power of 5 mW using a 785 nm laser line. For each Raman spectrum, between 50 and 200 single Raman spectra with a measuring time of 0.5 s were accumulated. Raman spectra were recorded within the spectral range of 0–2500 cm⁻¹ for Raman shift. Samples for SERS were prepared by adding 15 μL of 10⁻³ mM 4ABT to 1.5 mL of each sample (AuNOC@pNIPAM, AuNTPs@pNIPAM, AuSTs@pNIPAM, at a gold concentration of 0.5 mM). After 1 h, allowing thermodynamic equilibrium to be reached, the colloidal solution was centrifuged twice and redispersed in 1.5 mL of water. SERS was directly recorded from these suspensions.

2.3 Synthesis of Au nanoparticles

In a typical synthesis, 50 mL of a solution containing 0.5 mM HAuCl₄ and 5 mM BDAC were introduced into a 100 mL round bottom flask under low magnetic stirring (100 rpm). Subsequently, the solution was heated up to 75 °C, 85 °C or 95 °C. Then, 100 μL of 3BA were added into the mixture. After a suitable amount of time enough to allow the complete reduction of HAuCl₄ to Au(0) (see Table 1) the solution was allowed to cool down to room temperature. Finally, in order to remove the excess of 3BA and BDAC, the colloidal dispersion containing the Au nanoparticles was centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet was dispersed in 50 mL of 4 mM CTAC. The same procedure was followed for the syntheses at 1 mM and 1.5 mM HAuCl₄, keeping constant the amounts of BDAC and 3BA. Scheme 1 illustrates the synthesis of Au nanoparticles mediated by 3BA.

Table 1 Size of the AuNTPs and AuNOC synthesized at three different concentrations of HAuCl₄ at 75 °C (reaction times are also included). Percentage of triangular prisms, octahedra, decahedra and bigger particles obtained at 75, 85 and 95 °C at 0.5 mM of HAuCl₄

[HAuCl ₄]	75 °C						85 °C		95 °C	
	0.5 mM		1.0 mM		1.5 mM		0.5 mM		0.5 mM	
	23						15		7	
Time/min	nm	%								
AuNTPs	54.8	58	65.8	46	74.7	41	44.9	55	33.3	50
AuNOC	35.2	37	41.9	36	47.5	30	34.6	41	26.6	46
Decahedra		4		8		9		3		2
Big particles		1		10		20		1		2

Scheme 1 General procedure for the synthesis of vinyl-terminated gold nanoparticles and shape-separation by surfactant micelle induced depletion interaction. (top) Core@shell Au@pNIPAM fabrication and gold overgrowth (bottom).

2.4 Purification of AuNTPs and AuNOC

As mentioned in the Introduction, surfactant micelle depletion-induced flocculation was applied for the separation of gold nanoparticles by using CTAC as a surfactant. Taking into account that the temperature of the synthesis will affect the final particle size (see below), different CTAC concentrations were used in each case. We describe in this section the separation procedure for particles prepared at 1.5 mM HAuCl₄ and at 75 °C, 85 °C and 95 °C.

Synthesis at 75 °C. Initially, in order to remove the bigger particles generated during the Au synthesis, the colloidal dispersion was centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was redispersed in a 5 mL vial containing 2 mL of 100 mM CTAC. After 4 h at RT, a precipitate (containing bigger particles) was observed at the bottom of the vial, which was discarded (Scheme 1, separation 1). The supernatant, containing a mixture of prisms and octahedra, was again centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was redispersed in a 5 mL vial containing 2 mL of 175 mM CTAC. After 4 h the supernatant, containing AuNOC, was separated, and the precipitate formed at the bottom of the vial, containing AuNTPs, was redispersed in 10 mL of 100 mM CTAC (Scheme 1, separation 2).

Synthesis at 85 °C. The colloidal dispersion obtained at 85 °C was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was redispersed in 2 mL of 125 mM CTAC in order to promote the depletion of the bigger particles. The supernatant was concentrated (8000 rpm, 30 minutes) and redispersed in 2 mL of 200 mM CTAC in order to promote the depletion of AuNTPs while AuNOC will remain in solution.

Synthesis at 95 °C. The colloidal dispersion synthesized at 95 °C was centrifuged at 8500 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was redispersed in 2 mL of 200 mM CTAC in order to promote the depletion of the bigger particles. The supernatant was concentrated (8500 rpm, 30 minutes) and redispersed in 2 mL of 250 mM CTAC in order to promote the depletion of AuNTPs while AuNOC will remain in solution.

2.5 Synthesis of Au@pNIPAM and Au overgrowth

To carry out the encapsulation of gold prisms and octahedra within pNIPAM microgels, firstly, 10 mL of each Au colloidal dispersion ([Au] ≈ 5 mM) obtained after purification step was heated at 70 °C under a N₂ flow. Then *N*-isopropylacrylamide (0.1698 g, 100 mM) and *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide (0.0234 g, 10 mM) were added under magnetic stirring. After 15 min, the N₂ flow was removed and the polymerization was initiated by adding 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionamide) dihydrochloride (10 μL, 0.1 M in water). After 2 h at 70 °C, the turbid mixture was allowed to cool down to room temperature under stirring. Finally, to remove small oligomers, unreacted monomers as well as gold-free microgels, the dispersion was diluted with water (50 mL) and centrifuged (30 min at 5500 rpm), the resulting pellet was redispersed in water. This process was repeated 3 times.

The AuSTs@pNIPAM particles were obtained by following the same overgrowth procedure as that previously reported by Liz-Marzan *et al.*³⁴ To a 10 mL growth solution containing 0.5 mM HAuCl₄, 8 mM CTAB and 4 mM ascorbic acid, 0.5 mL of AuNTP@pNIPAM seed solution (1 mM in terms of gold) were added.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Synthesis and characterization of Au nanoparticles

As mentioned in the Introduction, only a few methods have been reported concerning the synthesis of gold nanoparticles with either triangular or octahedral morphologies in aqueous media. In addition, such synthesis procedures do not confer any surface functionality to the as prepared nanoparticles. In order to develop a one-step functionalization, and a highly reproducible methodology using HAuCl_4 as a gold source, we used 3BA in the presence of BDAC as a stabilizer. It should be noted that initially we used CTAC as a stabilizer, as in the previously mentioned methods. Unfortunately, highly polydisperse gold nanoparticle morphologies together with undefined morphologies were obtained (Fig. S1, ESI[†]). Then, we replace CTAC with BDAC, a surfactant with a similar structure, which contains a benzyl group instead of a methyl group in its structure. Initially, we analyzed the influence of the gold salt concentration and the temperature on the size and shape of gold nanoparticles (see Table 1).

First, we analyzed the effect of the gold salt precursor at a given temperature; initially, a precursor solution (see the Experimental section) was heated to 75 °C leading to a large number of well-defined AuNTPs (yield 58%) and AuNOC (yield

37%) (see Fig. 1A), along with a small number of decahedra and bigger particles (yield 4% and 1%, respectively). The average side length, determined by TEM analysis, was 54.8 ± 4.0 nm and 35.2 ± 2.5 nm for AuNTPs and AuNOC, respectively. Increasing the gold salt concentration to 1 mM leads also to AuNTPs and AuNOC nanoparticles (see Fig. 1B) with percentages of 46% and 36%, respectively (Table 1). Interestingly, a higher percentage (10%) of relatively big particles was also observed. The average dimension of the particles increases by 65.8 ± 3.9 nm and 41.9 ± 2.7 nm for AuNTPs and AuNOC, respectively (Table 1, Fig S2[†]). A similar trend was observed when the synthesis was performed with 1.5 mM HAuCl_4 (Fig. 1C), that is, the percentage of AuNTPs, AuNOC, decahedra and bigger particles decreased to 40%, 30%, 9% and 20%, respectively. On the other hand, the average side lengths for AuNTPs and AuNOC increased to 74.7 ± 5.6 nm and 47.5 ± 3.9 nm, respectively.

Fig. 1F shows the normalized UV-vis spectrum of the as prepared aqueous dispersion of gold nanoparticles synthesized at 75 °C in the presence of 0.5 mM, 1.0 mM and 1.5 mM HAuCl_4 . A clear red-shift in the position of the localized surface plasmon resonance from 569 to 583 nm is observed, which is produced by the increase in the average particle size.⁴⁵ The UV-vis spectra also show a broad shoulder located at longer

Fig. 1 TEM images of the gold nanoparticles synthesized at 75 °C under different concentrations of HAuCl_4 : (A) 0.5 mM, (B) 1.0 mM and (C) 1.5 mM. (D) 0.5 mM, 85 °C; (E) 0.5 mM, 95 °C. (F) UV-vis spectra of the three colloidal solutions synthesized at 75 °C at 0.5 (black line), 1.0 (red line) and 1.5 mM HAuCl_4 (blue line).

wavelengths (700–800 nm) for 1.0 and 1.5 mM HAuCl_4 , which can be ascribed to the presence of bigger particles. The intensity of the shoulder increases with the gold salt concentration in the reaction mixture, suggesting an increase in the percentage of bigger particles as confirmed by TEM analysis.

We also studied the influence of the temperature on the size and shape of the particles at a given gold salt concentration. We have chosen 0.5 mM HAuCl_4 since it gave rise to the lowest contamination of bigger particles. Overall, well-dispersed AuNTPs and AuNOC morphologies were found in all the studied cases. At 85 °C, the average side length of AuNTPs and AuNOC was 44.9 ± 3.7 and 34.6 ± 2.7 nm, respectively (see Fig. S4, ESI†). When the reaction temperature was raised to 95 °C, the average side length size decreased to 33.3 ± 3.0 nm and 26.6 ± 2.0 nm for AuNTPs and AuNOC, respectively. Fig. 1D and 1E show TEM images of the gold nanoparticles synthesized at 85 °C and 95 °C, respectively. This tendency suggests that an increase in the reaction temperature led to a higher nucleation rate, leading to smaller particles. Concerning the influence of temperature on the relative populations of AuNTPs and AuNOC, it should be noted that the percentage of AuNTPs decreased from 58% to 50% when the temperature was increased from 75 °C to 95 °C. On the other hand, the percentage of AuNOC increased from 37% to 46% (see Table 1).

We also studied the influence of temperature on the overall reaction rate. It is well known that temperature is a key parameter in the synthesis of metal nanoparticles since it can greatly modify the nucleation and growth steps. We have measured the time evolution of UV-vis spectra for the reaction at 75 °C, 85 °C and 95 °C in the presence of 0.5 mM HAuCl_4 , see Fig. 2. At the beginning only a band located at *ca.* 325 nm that corresponds to Au^{3+} is observed (black spectra in Fig. 2); upon the addition of 3BA this band decreases due to the progressive reduction to Au^+ , followed by the appearance of a new band around 500–600 nm, ascribed to the nucleation of gold

Fig. 2 UV-vis spectral evolution for the syntheses performed at 0.5 mM of HAuCl_4 at (A) 75 °C, (B) 85 °C and (C) 95 °C. Evolution of the absorbance at 400 nm for the three mentioned temperatures (D).

Fig. 3 Tilted FESEM images of the Au nanoprisms AuNOC synthesized at 0.5 mM of HAuCl_4 : (A) 75 °C, (B) 85 °C and (C) 95 °C. The white arrows show AuNOCs particles with different orientations.

nanoparticles. Subsequently, the band increases in intensity and becomes sharper and better defined due to the growth of the particles (Fig. 2A–C). Fig. 2D presents the increase of the absorbance at 400 nm with time at the three mentioned temperatures. The difference in the reaction rate can be easily observed; while at 75 °C the absorbance reached a maximum at 23 min; when the synthesis was performed at 85 °C and 95 °C the time need to reach the maximum absorbance decreased to 15 min and 7 min, respectively. It should be noted that in all cases the final UV-vis spectra showed a narrow localized surface plasmon band, suggesting the absence of bigger particles.

In order to completely characterize the morphology of the obtained particles, they have been analyzed by FESEM. Fig. 3 shows representative tilted FESEM images where the morphologies of AuNTPs and AuNOC nanoparticles can be clearly discerned. Additionally, a detailed study of the AuNTPs dimensions showed a slight decrease in particle thickness as a function of the temperature. The average thickness dimension decreased from 16.6 nm at 75 °C to 13.8 nm at 85 °C and 9.9 nm at 95 °C.

Finally, in order to demonstrate the reproducibility of this procedure, the synthesis procedure performed at 75 °C (0.5 mM HAuCl_4) was scale-up to 250 mL, giving rise to similar results in size, reaction rate and percentage of the main morphologies (Fig. S5, ESI†).

2.2 Purification of gold nanoparticles

Surfactant micelle induced depletion interaction has been previously reported for the separation of metal nanoparticles containing different sizes and shapes. This method is based on the depletion interactions between particles in the presence of micelles produced by a surfactant.⁴⁵ We carried out the separation process for samples prepared with 1.5 mM of HAuCl_4 at the three mentioned temperatures. Initially, bigger particles were flocculated with 100 mM CTAC, as was confirmed by the TEM images and UV-vis spectrum of the redispersed precipitate (Fig. S6, ESI†). The remaining supernatant, mainly containing AuNTPs and AuNOC, was subjected to the same separation procedure but with 175 mM CTAC. After this second depletion process the precipitate contained mainly AuNTPs (see Fig. 4A) while the supernatant contained AuNOC (see Fig. 4B). As can be clearly observed the percentage of either prisms or octahedra remarkably increases compared

Fig. 4 (A) and (B) TEM images of the AuNTPs and AuNOC (75 °C and 1.5 mM HAuCl_4) after depletion-induced flocculation, respectively. (C) and (D) TEM images of the Au NTPs (1.5 mM HAuCl_4) after the purification step, synthesized at 85 °C and 95 °C, respectively. (E) Top view and cross section (inset) of an AuNTP showing flat top and bottom facets. The scale in the inset is 20 nm. (F) Selected area electron diffraction pattern obtained from the AuNTP; in the inset we show the prism with the in plane rotation compensated for.

with the sample before purification steps (see Fig. 1C). Images at lower magnification are shown in Fig. S7, ESI†. TEM images corresponding to the AuNTPs synthesized at 85 °C and 95 °C are included in Fig. 4C and D, respectively. As is observed, the number of prisms remarkably increases with respect to samples before depletion. The dimension analysis for the obtained Au prisms resulted in an average side length of 52.3 ± 3.5 nm, and 42.3 ± 3.2 nm for synthesis at 85 and 95 °C, respectively (Fig S8, ESI†), data not included in Table 1. The crystallographic structure of the AuNTPs has also been analyzed by HR-TEM. A representative top view TEM image of an AuNTP lying flat on the carbon film is presented in Fig. 4E. Prisms show an almost perfect triangular shape with rounded tips. The inset shows a cross section of one of the prisms exhibiting a thickness of 43 nm and lateral side facets. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns, included in Fig. 4F, display a regular reciprocal net that corresponds with the $[111]$ zone axis of the gold crystalline structure. In the inset we show an AuNTP with the in plane rotation compensated for; from that we have found the $[211]$ type directions as the crystalline directions parallel to the prisms tips.

The purification process was also monitored by UV-vis spectroscopy. Fig. 5 presents the normalized UV-vis spectra of the Au colloidal solutions of the samples prepared at 75 °C and 1.5 mM of HAuCl_4 , before and after depletion induced separ-

Fig. 5 Normalized UV-vis spectra of the Au nanoparticles synthesized at 75 °C and 1.5 mM of HAuCl_4 before (black line) and after depletion-induced flocculation, which includes AuNOC (red line) and AuNTPs (blue line). The inset shows an image of a vial containing the AuNTPs and AuNOC colloidal solutions.

ation processes. Initially the spectrum exhibits a maximum plasmon band at 583 nm (black line), and the aqueous colloidal solution displayed a purple color, the inset in Fig. 5.

After purification, the normalized UV-vis spectrum of the isolated AuNOC displays a narrow plasmon band at 554 nm (red line) and the aqueous colloidal solution (included in the inset) shows an intense red color. The normalized UV-vis spectrum of the AuNTPs shows a plasmon band at 602 nm (blue line), and the aqueous colloidal solution displayed an intense blue color.

3.3 Synthesis of Au@pNIPAM particles. SERS investigations

As was mentioned, 3BA supplies vinyl-functionalization onto the gold nanoparticle surface.⁴² It is important to remark that double bond terminated systems are nowadays used for different purposes; for example, double bond terminated specimens have been recently incorporated on the H-Si surface by photoactivated hydrosilylation reaction,⁴⁶ and vinyl-functionalized metal nanoparticles have been encapsulated with a pNIPAM, styrene or silica shell. To achieve this aim, the purified samples containing AuNTPs and AuNOC were subjected to free radical polymerization in the presence of *N*-isopropylacrylamide and *N,N'*-methylenebisacrylamide. Fig. 6A and 6B show representative TEM images of the obtained core@shell AuNTPs@pNIPAM and AuNOC@pNIPAM nanocomposites. Both AuNTPs and AuNOC are homogeneously coated with a pNIPAM shell. After that, in order to increase the number of tips within the microgel, AuNTPs@pNIPAM particles were used as seeds for the Au core overgrowth, under the same conditions as those previously reported for Au@pNIPAM particles,³⁴ resulting in AuSTs@pNIPAM nanoparticles (Fig. 6C). It should be noted that in this case the initial seeds are formed by AuNTPs@pNIPAM; the resulting gold cores in

the AuSTs@pNIPAM system contain higher number and sharper tips, compared with gold nanostars grown from Au spheres.³⁴

SERS investigations were performed by using 4-aminobenzenethiol (4ABT) as the model analyte. Fig. 6D includes the 785 nm SERS spectra of 1.0×10^{-5} M 4ABT for the three different samples. In all specimens the Raman peaks corresponding to 4ABT were clearly observed,⁴⁷ including the peaks at 1592 (CC stretching), 1489 (CC stretching + CH bending), 1225, 1176 and 1135 (CH bending), 1080 (CS stretching), 1005 (CC + CCC bending), 822 and 702 (CH, CS and CC wagging) and 636 cm^{-1} (CCC bending). As expected the SERS intensity increases with the number of tips present in the metal core. The inset presents the SERS spectra of 4ABT in the spectral range between 1000 and 1200 cm^{-1} , the intensities of the 4ABT signal follow the expected tendency AuSTs@pNIPAM < AuNTPs@pNIPAM > AuNOC@pNIPAM.

4. Conclusions

We have presented a novel, easy and reproducible seedless method for the synthesis of vinyl-terminated Au nanoparticles in water media by using 3-butenic acid as a reducing agent and BDAC as a stabilizer. This method produces triangular prisms and octahedra as principal morphologies. The reaction rate was monitored by UV-vis evolution at three different temperatures (75, 85 and 95 °C). UV-vis measurements demonstrated that the reaction rate of particles is higher when the temperature of the synthesis is increased. TEM analysis confirmed that both the average side length of the particles and the amount of big morphologies increase with the concentration of HAuCl_4 . On the contrary, the particle size and the percentage of Au prisms decrease with the temperature. FESEM analysis showed 3D images, which confirmed that the particle thickness of AuNTPs also decreased with the temperature. Surfactant micelle induced depletion interaction was used as a purification step. This method was able to separate the different morphologies and increased the percentage of Au prisms and octahedra up to ~90%. The vinyl-terminated Au prisms and octahedra were easily encapsulated within a pNIPAM microgel by free radical polymerization, obtaining a hybrid Au@pNIPAM system. The number of tips within the microgel was increased by gold overgrowth under controlled conditions, resulting in an AuSTs@pNIPAM system. SERS investigations demonstrated that Au@pNIPAM particles containing greater numbers of high curvature sites provided improved SERS responses. The method proposed is the first reported procedure for the synthesis of Au nanoprisms and octahedra which enables a direct incorporation of a pNIPAM shell.

Fig. 6 Representative TEM images of different core@shell hybrid systems. (A) AuNTPs@pNIPAM, (B) AuNOC@pNIPAM and (C) AuSTs@pNIPAM particles. (D) Raman spectra of 4ABT (10^{-5} M) aqueous solution adsorbed on the different samples tested. The scale in the inset is 50 nm. The inset in (D) highlights the Raman shift located at 1080 cm^{-1} .

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